

The Case Study of India's Human Resources with Respect to Business and Managerial Manpower

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ABSTRACT: The present paper aims at analyzing the position and placement of various management and business degree holders who are postgraduate from different management institutes running in the different parts the India under the affiliation of the Indian universities and open universities. Among management and business degree holders the trend in their placement is constantly declining in Indian universities as compared to Indian Open University universities with respect to ratio of their admissions taken by the students. Notwithstanding a strong human resource base of the Indian labour market manifesting in a highly skilled reserve of business and management manpower. The live records of placement agencies present a dismal figure about the absorption of this precious managerial and trained human resources of our country, as reflected in the increasing number of job seekers. But one thing it has to be noticed that business and management personnel with postgraduate qualification.

Keywords: - placement agencies, management, qualification, manpower and universities

INTRODUCTION:-

Recent theories of development suggest that for developing countries to catch up with the affluent industrialized countries, emphasis has to shift from merely industrialization and diversification "to an emphasis on building up managerial capacity, entrepreneurial skills and human capital in general". Quoting with the examples developed countries like Germany and Japan caught up with other developed European and OECD (Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development) countries, as also the contemporary example of South -East Asian countries, which fortified their economic base with stronger managerial capabilities especially in human capital. Their strong economic structures and accumulated human capital alone enabled them to revive from the crises of Second World War with surprising speed (Raffer and Singer, 2001). Right since independence, the Indian planners contemplated to silhouette India's strategy of attaining economic and commercially technical self reliance, with the grooming home grown commercial and technical manpower. That is why; the Nehruvian model of development envisaged an outright thrust on the erection of a well knit chain of IIM's to harness the vast potential of human skill and technical power of the Indian work force, by chiseling and honing their knowledge and skills in these 'temples of learning'. Although the accumulation of physical capital is important in the process of economic growth of a country, but as a matter of fact, the growth of tangible capital stock

itself depends extensively on the rate of human capital formation. In the absence of adequate absorption of human capital, even the utilization of physical capital will be impaired, leading to stunted development. Absorption and placement of appropriate form of human capital formations implies and development of abilities and skills among the productive workforce of a country. The human capital formation is described as "the process of acquiring and increasing the number of persons who have the skills, educational and experience, which are critical for the economic and political development of the country. Human capital formations are thus associated with investment in man and his development as a creative and productive resource" (Harbison, 1992). In order to transform the liability of huge size of population into assets, adoptions of different measures of human capital formation is essential. For that the country is taking the help of different technical and non-technical universities situated in different parts of the country to impart technical education in business, management and commercial fields, with the aim of developing critical skill.

Increasing number of job seekers, especially in areas concerning business and management technology, manifest gross squandering of highly skill and technical human resource. It betrays a moronic mismatch between manpower generation and its absorption in country's productive and non-productive sector.

THE OBJECTIVES ARE AS FOLLOWS:-

1. To study the number of student belonging to various faculties taking admission in the post graduate programme of business management in various institutes of Indian universities and open universities.
2. To study the number of students getting passed out after completing the post graduate programme of business management in various institutes of Indian universities and open universities.
3. To study of placement of the number of students completing the post graduate programme of business management in various institutes of Indian universities and open universities

4. METHODOLOGY:-

Area under study

With a geographical area 53,485 Km², spread across 13 districts, is unique in its topography and large rural population which is 75% of total. The study was conducted in the year 2012 of Uttarakhand.

Design Study:-

The study was conducted in state of Uttarakhand. The data was collected from the educated respondents of Uttarakhand who were readers and viewers of newspapers, television, magazines and

THE ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA:-

Table:-1. Number of students admitted in M.B.A Course of universities belonging to different faculties.

Universities of India	Number of seats	2008-09					2009-2010					2010-2011					
		B ₁	B ₂	B ₃	B ₄	B ₅	B ₁	B ₂	B ₃	B ₄	B ₅	B ₁	B ₂	B ₃	B ₄	B ₅	
University of Allahabad	46	7(15.2)	8(17.3)	9(19.5)	10(21.7)	12(26.3)	6(13.1)	9(19.5)	11(23.9)	1(2.2)	8(17.3)	9(19.5)	8(17.3)	1(2.2)	1(2.2)	1(2.2)	4(8.7)
C.C.S. Uni. Meerut	60	14(23.4)	12(20)	10(16.6)	16(26.6)	8(13.4)	9(15)	14(23.4)	17(28.2)	8(13.4)	1(2)	7(11.6)	1(2)	4(6.6)	6(10)	30(50)	
B.R.A .Uni., Agra	60	13(22)	9(15)	15(25)	11(18.3)	12(20)	11(18.3)	8(13.3)	18(30)	0(0)	2(3.3)	0(0)	1(1.6)	1(1.6)	1(1.6)	22(36.6)	

internet etc. The residents of these parties were expected to have high literacy rate, its residents are expected to be ideal respondents for deep study of this type. A study of 325, respondents were taken from these for state of Uttarakhand, which was selected on the basis of purposive sampling. Purposive sampling is justified for exploratory study .When the choice of the individual teams of a sample entirely depends on the discretion of the investigation it is called a purposive sampling .In this type, the members constituting the sample are chosen not according to some definite scientific procedure but according to convince and personal choice of the individuals who selected the sample.

Population under study:-

From total 325 respondents were selected on the basis of purposive sampling. After identifying the respondents the information was obtained from it.

Sampling and sample size:-

A total number of 325 audiences were selected using purposive sampling procedure.

Methods of data collection:-

Data will be collected with the help of specific research tools (1) observation, (2) interview (3) interview schedule (4) records (5) secondary information would be collected from the T.V., newspaper, magazine and internet.

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Note:- Number in Parentheses=%; B₁= Bachelor of Science; B₂= Bachelor of Arts; B₃= Bachelor of Commerce; ; B₄= Bachelor of Business Administration; ; B₅= Bachelor of other streams(courses).

Table:-2. .Number of students admitted in the M.B.A course of Open University belonging to different faculties.

Open Universities of India	Number of seats	2008-09					2009-2010					2010-2011				
		B ₁	B ₂	B ₃	B ₄	B ₅	B ₁	B ₂	B ₃	B ₄	B ₅	B ₁	B ₂	B ₃	B ₄	B ₅
Rajshri Tandon Open University	180	35(19.4)	37(20.5)	31(17.3)	49(27.3)	28(15.5)	31(17.3)	29(16.1)	40(22.2)	33(18.3)	47(26.1)	34(18.4)	3(7.0)	43(23.4)	3(2.0)	33(18.9)
Bhuj Open University	120	20(16.6)	26(21.6)	31(25.8)	29(24.4)	14(11.6)	16(16.6)	21(17.5)	24(23.5)	32(26.6)	19(15.8)	22(18.5)	3(2.5)	40(33.6)	0(0.6)	19(15.5)
Indra Gandhi Open University	120	25(20.8)	21(17.5)	23(19.2)	18(15)	33(27.5)	29(24.1)	30(25)	16(13.3)	34(28.3)	11(9.3)	15(12.4)	2(1.9)	28(23.1)	3(2.4)	20(16.6)

Note:- Number in Parentheses=%; B₁= Bachelor of Science; B₂= Bachelor of Arts; B₃= Bachelor of Commerce; ; B₄= Bachelor of Business Administration; ; B₅= Bachelor of other streams(courses).

Table:-3. .Number of students completed M.B.A course of universities belonging to different faculties

Universities of India	2008-09					2009-2010					2010-2011				
	B ₁	B ₂	B ₃	B ₄	B ₅	B ₁	B ₂	B ₃	B ₄	B ₅	B ₁	B ₂	B ₃	B ₄	B ₅
University of Allahabad	3	3	5	7	6	2	4	7	5	4	4	3	5	6	1
C.C.S. Uni. Meerut	9	5	4	8	4	4	7	9	3	4	3	5	2	2	17
B.R.A .Uni.,	5	4	6	6	5	6	3	7	00	1	00	8	6	4	11

Agra											5					
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Note:-B₁= Bachelor of Science; B₂= Bachelor of Arts; B₃= Bachelor of Commerce; ; B₄= Bachelor of Business Administration; ; B₅= Bachelor of other streams(courses).

Table:-4. .Number of students completed M.B.A course from Open Universities belonging to different faculties

Open Universities of India	2008-09					2009-2010					2010-2011				
	B ₁	B ₂	B ₃	B ₄	B ₅	B ₁	B ₂	B ₃	B ₄	B ₅	B ₁	B ₂	B ₃	B ₄	B ₅
Rajshri Tandon Open University	27	22	25	37	29	23	18	33	26	3	21	25	29	32	26
Bhuj Open University	15	19	24	21	7	9	11	18	23	1	12	14	21	33	3
Indra Gandhi Open University	16	11	13	10	8	25	26	8	22	20	9	11	12	21	13

Note:-B₁= Bachelor of Science; B₂= Bachelor of Arts; B₃= Bachelor of Commerce; ; B₄= Bachelor of Business Administration; ; B₅= Bachelor of other streams(courses).

Table:-5. .Number of students getting placement after completing M.B.A course from Universities belonging to different faculties

University of India	2008-09					2009-2010					2010-2011				
	B ₁	B ₂	B ₃	B ₄	B ₅	B ₁	B ₂	B ₃	B ₄	B ₅	B ₁	B ₂	B ₃	B ₄	B ₅
University of Allahabad	2	0	3	7	4	2	4	4	5	3	2	1	4	5	0
C.C.S. Uni. Meerut	5	1	1	3	0	2	3	5	1	2	0	1	1	1	6

B.R.A .Uni., Agra	2	2	4	6	3	3	1	4	0	8	0	3	4	2	4
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Note:-B₁= Bachelor of Science; B₂= Bachelor of Arts; B₃= Bachelor of Commerce; ; B₄= Bachelor of Business Administration; ; B₅= Bachelor of other streams(courses).

Table:-6. Number of students getting placement after completing M.B.A course from Open Universities belonging to different faculties

Open University of India	2008-09					2009-2010					2010-2011				
	B ₁	B ₂	B ₃	B ₄	B ₅	B ₁	B ₂	B ₃	B ₄	B ₅	B ₁	B ₂	B ₃	B ₄	B ₅
Rajshri Tandon Open University	17	14	18	20	12	13	8	23	18	25	9	7	12	24	12
Bhuj Open University	10	8	14	17	3	7	5	12	17	4	6	5	12	6	1
Indra Gandhi Open University	10	5	9	8	4	14	13	5	18	4	7	5	8	15	7

Note:-B₁= Bachelor of Science; B₂= Bachelor of Arts; B₃= Bachelor of Commerce; ; B₄= Bachelor of Business Administration; ; B₅= Bachelor of other streams(courses)

Result /conclusion: - the different parts of the India under the affiliation of the Indian universities and open universities. Among management and business degree holders the trend in their placement is constantly escalating in Indian universities as compared to Indian Open universities with respect to ratio of their admissions taken by the students.

Reference:-

AICTE (2002).Background document, National Consultation on the future of technical education in India, New Delhi

Chadha, G.K(2004). "Human capital base of the Indian labor market: Identifying worry spots"; Indian journal of labor economics, Vol.47 no.1pp124

Choudhury,S (2004). "Twenty percent engineers in the country are without jobs" Hindustan times nuv.08 p.6.

Hartley J (1994). Case Studies in Organizational Research in C. Cassell & G. Symon (eds.) Qualitative Methods in Organizational Research: A Practical Guide: London: Sage, 208-226

Sen, Ratna (1996) Workers' Management: Some industrial cooperative experiences. Calcutta: Subarnarekha

- Editorial (2004) “of unemployable engineers: quality supply must meet industry’s needs” The tribune nov.9p10
- Parikh, P.P. And S.P. Sukhumi (2002) Women in engineering profession in India-the millennium scenario, New Delhi: Department of science and technology
- Parikh, P.P. And S.P. Sukhumi (2004) “Women engineering in India “Economic and political weekly, vol.XXX no. 2, Jan10 pp193-201
- Raffer, K.and H.W.Singer(2001) The economic north –south divide: Six decades of unequal development ,Cheltenham, U.K.: Edward Elgar ,pp17-20
- Roy, S,(2004) “Teacher, don’t leave them kids alone”. The economic times , nov.10 p.4